

Training courses on RDM for researchers as a cross-location task

The RDM curriculum of the UA Ruhr

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Abstract

In order to be able to conduct research data management (RDM) adequately, researchers should have an overview of the most important measures: from data management plans and storage options on site and beyond, to the allocation of metadata and tools for working with data and processing data. In order to support researchers, there are service centers for RDM at many scientific institutions, whose core business includes not only consulting but also the provision of training courses to build up knowledge. The requirements for such a service are manifold: it must be structured and adapted to the needs of the researchers - in terms of time, content and didactics. It should be flexible and low-threshold enough to appeal to researchers from different disciplines and with different levels of prior knowledge. It should arouse interest in RDM and also offer added value for which it is worth investing time in training. This complexity presents service centers with the challenge of being able to provide such a service with both specialist expertise and sufficient personnel capacity.

The RDM curriculum of the University Alliance (UA) Ruhr [1] is an innovative example of an evolved training program that offers researchers thematic breadth and temporal flexibility through modularity and ensures quality and saves resources through cross-location cooperation.

The curriculum offered jointly each semester by employees of the RDM service centers at Ruhr University Bochum (RUB), TU Dortmund University and the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE) is based on a combination of face-to-face and online basic training courses and supplementary advanced courses. The basic courses provide a broad foundation of knowledge and offer participants the opportunity to network beyond their own location and discipline. In the advanced training courses, more specific topics are addressed in a practical manner and the use of tools is actively trained in hands-on workshops. The award of an RDM-badge after successful participation in a basic training course and two advanced courses provides proof of RDM knowledge and creates an additional incentive to participate. With around 20 events in the summer semester 2025, it has been possible to provide an attractive selection of both

disciplinary and interdisciplinary training courses for researchers and to use the available resources and expertise in a targeted manner.

In our conference contribution, we want to show how the RDM curriculum, designed at the UDE and implemented for the first time in the winter semester 2022/2023 [2] [3], has successfully developed as an example of best practice in a regional cooperation task with the RUB and TU Dortmund University in the context of the UA Ruhr. Based on the initial conceptual considerations, the advantages and challenges of this cross-university cooperation will be presented with a particular focus on the program and the organization. With an outlook, we want to show how the RDM curriculum as a model has the potential for further expansion: an opening for researchers outside the UA Ruhr.

Keywords: RDM, training, collaboration

Resources

RDM training group / UA Ruhr, "RDM Curriculum of the UA Ruhr", 2025, <https://www.uni-due.de/rds/en/rdmcurriculum.php>

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JSt: [Writing – original draft](#); all authors: [Writing – review & editing](#); all authors: [Conceptualization](#)

Competing interests

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References

- [1] J. Stapels, T. Güden-Silber, J. Stegemann, „Modulare standortübergreifende Schulungsangebote: Das FDM-Curriculum der Universitätsallianz Ruhr“, Poster E-Science-Tage 2025, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.11588/heidok.00036253>
- [2] S. Leimer, S. Hendriks, L. Korte, J. Stegemann, S. A. Stock, H. Timm, S. Rehwald, “Research Data Management Curriculum of the Research Data Services at the University Library Duisburg-Essen”, Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, 1. 12-14 September 2023, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.209>
- [3] S. Leimer, S. Hendriks, L. Korte, J. Stegemann, S. A. Stock, H. Timm, S. Rehwald, „Forschungsdatenmanagement-Curriculum der Research Data Services an der Universitätsbibliothek Duisburg-Essen (Preprint)“, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.17185/dupublico/83316>